

Impact of Cloud Computing Technology on Developing the Performance of the External Auditor

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Abstract

The research aimed to identify the impact of cloud computing technology on improving the performance of the external auditor. This was achieved by identifying its role in strengthening the impartiality of the external auditor, as well as its role in increasing the efficiency of the external auditor. The research found a positive influence relationship between the independent variable of cloud computing technology and the dependent variable of improving the performance of the external auditor. The application of cloud computing technology has a clear impact on strengthening the impartiality of the external auditor. Furthermore, the application of cloud computing technology leads to the ease and speed of completing work with impartiality by the external auditor, and has an impact on increasing the efficiency of the external auditor. It also contributes to reducing the time required to access financial data, thus increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of auditing.

Keywords: *Cloud computing technology, external auditor performance.*

JEL Classification codes: *H83, M42.*

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Introduction

Given the tremendous developments witnessed in the field of information technology and artificial intelligence systems, cloud computing has gained global attention. Smart systems offer innovative solutions that reduce time, reduce costs, and improve work efficiency. This has prompted many auditors to keep pace with the necessary technological developments and acquire the technological skills required to deal with such developments and enhance the auditing profession (Mohammed, 2023: 144). The auditing profession is characterized by continuity, development, and continuous updating, due to competition among practitioners and the rapid developments surrounding audit firms. This calls for them to keep pace with technological developments to improve their performance in a way that ensures the efficient and effective provision of auditing services and

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increases user confidence in their reports (Al-Haddad, 2022). The role of external auditors is also crucial in developing a further understanding of this new technology, in addition to advising their companies on related risks.

Methodology

Research Problem

The research problem was to understand the impact of cloud computing technology on improving the performance of the external auditor. What benefits will audit firms gain from implementing cloud computing technology, which helps strengthen the impartiality of the external auditor and enhance their efficiency? Accordingly, the research problem can be formulated with the following main question: What is the impact of cloud computing technology on improving the performance of the external auditor? From this main question, the following two sub-questions can be formulated:

1. Does cloud computing technology play a role in strengthening the impartiality of the external auditor?
2. Does cloud computing technology play a role in increasing the efficiency of the external auditor?

Research Importance

The particular importance of this research is evident in its importance in identifying the impact of cloud computing technology on improving the performance of external auditors. This research examines a topic of great importance, shedding light on the critical importance of the external auditor profession. It also highlights cloud computing technology as a new and modern policy, making this topic of particular importance. It can also be used by future students and researchers as a reliable source for scientific research.

Research Objectives

Based on the problem and importance of the research, the research objectives can be summarized as follows:

1. To identify the impact of cloud computing technology on improving the performance of the external auditor.
2. To identify the role of cloud computing technology in strengthening the impartiality of the external auditor.
3. To identify the role of cloud computing technology in increasing the efficiency of the external auditor.

Research Hypothesis

To address its problem and align with its objectives, the research relies on the following main hypothesis: There is a statistically significant effect between the application of cloud computing technology and the improvement of external auditor performance. Based on the previous main hypothesis, the following two sub-hypotheses can be derived:

1. There is a statistically significant effect between the application of cloud computing technology and strengthening the impartiality of the external auditor.
2. There is a statistically significant effect between the application of cloud computing technology and increasing the efficiency of the external auditor.

Figure 1. Hypothetical Diagram of the Research Variables
 Source: Prepared by researchers

Research Limits

1. Temporal Limits: The research period spanned the year 2024.
2. Spatial Limits: Some audit firms in Iraq.
3. Subject Limits: A study of the impact of cloud computing technology on improving external auditor performance.

Literature Review

First: Cloud computing technology

Conceptual Framework of Cloud Computing:

Cloud computing has significantly reshaped the way software is deployed and managed, marking a fundamental transition from conventional IT infrastructures toward more flexible and adaptive environments. The concept of the "cloud," as referenced in this study, is believed to have originated from network diagrams that symbolized the Internet or specific components of it. Within this framework, cloud computing illustrates the transfer of applications and services through the Internet medium. Although the notion of cloud computing may be traced back to the era of shared computing resources and remote application access, its modern interpretation encompasses a wide range of Internet-based services and solutions. Notably, the end-user devices employed to connect with these services typically do not necessitate specialized software installations.

The core principle of cloud computing lies in shifting IT services from local desktop environments to centralized remote data centers. Its deployment models span a wide spectrum, ranging from enterprise-level business solutions to modern mobile applications. Through this approach, users gain on-demand access to computing infrastructure without the burden of local installation or maintenance. Conceptually, cloud computing (CC) represents a performance-oriented IT framework that integrates multiple existing technologies and paradigms, including virtualization, grid computing, autonomic systems, and pay-per-use pricing mechanisms (Foster et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2010).

From the above, it can be said that cloud computing is the use of digital information technology in auditing operations to help auditors store files so they can be easily accessed when needed, with minimal time and cost.

Key Characteristics of Cloud Computing

Several defining characteristics contribute to positioning cloud computing as one of the most rapidly expanding fields within today's global economy (Mohammad et al., 2024).

- a. Resource pooling represents a fundamental principle of cloud computing. It refers to the capacity of cloud service providers to allocate and distribute computing resources among multiple users while ensuring that each client receives a tailored set of services aligned with their specific needs. This multi-tenant model can be implemented in areas such as processing power, bandwidth allocation, and data storage. Importantly, the dynamic management of resources in real time occurs seamlessly, without disrupting the end-user experience.
- b. On-demand self-service is regarded as one of the most essential characteristics of cloud computing. It empowers users to independently manage and monitor computing resources such as server capacity, uptime, and available network storage. This feature represents a core advantage of cloud computing, as it allows customers to dynamically adjust processing power and other resources in response to their specific needs.
- c. Ease of maintenance: One of the best things about the cloud is that servers are easy to maintain, with very little, if any, downtime. Cloud-based resources are constantly updated to enhance their capabilities. Upgrades run faster than previous iterations and are more compatible with hardware.
- d. Rapid scalability and elasticity are among the most significant benefits of cloud computing. This capability allows organizations to efficiently run resource-intensive workloads for limited durations at a lower cost. Such workloads are widely adopted by users, and thanks to the scalability of cloud services, they can be managed flexibly and in a cost-effective manner.
- e. Cost efficiency is another defining characteristic of cloud computing. By adopting this model, organizations can significantly reduce their IT expenditures. Customers are only charged for the administrative and operational costs associated with the resources they actually consume, without hidden fees or unexpected expenses.
- f. Metering and reporting services are among the key advantages that make cloud computing an attractive choice for businesses. This functionality allows both service providers and clients to track the usage of cloud resources, detailing how and for what purposes the services are utilized. Such transparency facilitates accurate billing, enhances resource management, and optimizes overall utilization.
- g. Data security represents a critical aspect of cloud computing. Cloud services often maintain redundant copies of data to prevent loss. In case data is corrupted or lost on one server, the duplicate copy stored on another server ensures recovery. This capability is particularly valuable when multiple users collaborate on the same file simultaneously, protecting against accidental corruption or deletion.

Sustainable Development of Cloud Computing

Sustainable development gains significance from its focus on the responsible utilization of resources across environmental, social, and economic dimensions (Rahman, 2022). By adopting cloud computing, organizations can decrease their reliance on local data centers, which are often energy-intensive and contribute to carbon emissions. Furthermore, cloud-based technologies promote sustainable practices by facilitating remote work and collaborative efforts (Goswami & Behera, 2021). The use of cloud-enabled collaboration tools also helps minimize paper consumption and other resource expenditures.

Types of Cloud Computing

There are three types of cloud computing, as stated by Kuyoro (2011):

a. Private Cloud

A private cloud is a term increasingly used by vendors to describe cloud-like services deployed within an organization's internal network. It is hosted on the organization's own data center, where scalable resources and virtualized applications provided by the cloud vendor are consolidated for exclusive use by authorized users. Unlike a public cloud, all resources and applications in a private cloud are managed internally, functioning similarly to an intranet. Due to its restricted internal access, a private cloud can offer enhanced security compared to public cloud solutions, as only the organization and designated stakeholders are permitted to access and operate within it.

b. Public Cloud

A public cloud refers to the conventional model of cloud computing, where computing resources are provisioned dynamically on a self-service basis over the Internet through web applications or web services, and managed by a third-party provider. These resources are shared among multiple users, with costs typically based on a pay-per-use scheme, similar to metered utilities, offering flexibility to accommodate varying demand. While the public cloud provides scalability and convenience, it is generally considered less secure than private or hybrid clouds, as users and providers must ensure that applications and data are protected from potential cyber threats.

c. Hybrid Cloud

A hybrid cloud is an integrated cloud environment that connects a private cloud to one or more external public cloud services, managed centrally and provisioned as a unified system within a secure network boundary. It delivers virtual IT solutions by leveraging both private and public cloud resources. Hybrid clouds offer enhanced security and control over data and applications while enabling authorized parties to access information via the Internet. They feature an open architecture that allows interoperability with other management systems. Hybrid cloud configurations can range from combining local devices, such as personal computers, with cloud services, to integrating virtual, physical, and clustered resources. For instance, a primarily virtual environment may still rely on physical servers, routers, or network devices functioning as firewalls or spam filters.

Advantages of Cloud Computing

Cloud computing has become a cornerstone of the contemporary IT landscape, supporting countless operational functions across industries. Predictions indicate that the majority of future workloads will reside in the cloud. In response, companies are recalibrating their capabilities and strategies to harness the flexibility and cost-effectiveness inherent in cloud infrastructure, which are essential for sustainability and competitiveness (Veronin et al., 2020). Hirenkumar et al., 2024, argue that the most prominent advantages of cloud computing can be summarized as follows:

- a. One of the most exciting focuses of cloud computing technology is its versatility.
- b. Its ability to submit and monitor requests from any location creates a more flexible and responsive work environment.
- c. Cloud computing opens the door to advanced developments such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data analytics.
- d. Cloud computing reduces geographical boundaries, enables real-time collaboration across diverse regions, and supports the transfer of departmental data to a global customer base with minimal effort.

e. Cloud computing offers the necessary flexibility in terms of users' ability to access multiple applications and services and share resources through the services of this modern technology (Tayseer, 2023).

Limitations of Cloud Computing

Alongside its advantages, cloud storage also presents several disadvantages and associated risks. Some of the key drawbacks are outlined below (Peshraw & Asaf, 2019).

- a. Leaks and unauthorized access to data between virtual machines running on the same server.
- b. Mistakes on the part of cloud providers in properly managing and storing sensitive data.
- c. Cloud services may occasionally experience prolonged periods of unavailability due to system errors or maintenance activities, which can disrupt business operations.
- d. There is a risk that malicious actors could compromise cloud-hosted applications, potentially gaining unauthorized access to sensitive client data and distributing it unlawfully.
- e. Dependence on cloud services introduces potential reliability issues, as service interruptions or performance inconsistencies may affect operational continuity.
- f. Maintaining the accuracy and consistency of stored information can be challenging, and there is a possibility that data integrity may be compromised.
- g. Limited configurations: Public cloud solution vendors have a standard arrangement of basic configurations that meet the needs of the general population. In some cases, exceptionally specialized hardware is required to handle the escalating computational challenges. In such cases, the use of public cloud solutions is often impossible, on the grounds that the required functionality is simple and not offered by the vendor.

Second: External Auditor Performance

The Concept of External Audit:

The external audit process has gained importance due to its objective, as it aims to verify and ensure the validity and accuracy of companies' financial records and information. Furthermore, it is a crucial and effective component of the global financial system, ensuring the integrity and complete transparency of companies' financial operations. Therefore, investors and stakeholders can confidently base their decisions on reliable information.

During an external audit, the auditor carefully evaluates the company's accounting systems and internal controls and compares them to internationally accepted accounting standards. As a result of this careful evaluation, the auditor seeks to ensure that the financial records fairly represent the economic events and transactions conducted by the company throughout the audit period. In doing so, the external auditor is able to identify potential risks and irregularities.

External auditing has been defined as a system that aims to express an objective opinion on reports and procedures related to preserving the property of the company subject to auditing (Muhammad, 2002).

It has also been defined as a systematic examination of a company by a specialized, independent person, who in turn certifies all audited operations, verifies the company's application of basic standards and rules, and examines internal control procedures. The purpose of this process is to prepare a final, detailed report containing their impartial opinion on the status of the company they audited (Pascal, 2006). We can say that external auditing involves a person from outside the

organization examining the organization's procedures and reports with complete objectivity and impartiality, and then preparing the final report on the organization's reality.

The Importance of External Auditing

The primary purpose of external auditing is to verify that a company's financial information has been fairly prepared and to provide reliable information to various stakeholders, such as investors, credit institutions, and regulatory authorities. This gives companies confidence in their financial soundness and provides investors with stable and reliable standards when making investment decisions. (Abdullah, 2022) believes that the importance of external auditing includes the following:

- a. Provides credibility: Verifying data can lead to greater credibility compared to unverified data. Audited accounts are more secure and provide confidence that they are free of errors.
- b. Provides confidence to shareholders: An independent external audit of financial statements can provide transparency to shareholders and ensure that the organization is being managed in their best interests.
- c. Ensures the quality of financial information: The external auditor plays a significant and effective role in ensuring the quality of an organization's financial information. They form an opinion on the accuracy and reliability of the organization's financial information and provide recommendations to improve the quality of financial information (ISA, 2020).

External Audit Steps

- a. Planning Phase: Determining the scope and method of the audit, identifying significant risks, and developing an audit strategy.
- b. Implementation Phase: The audit is actually conducted according to the established audit strategy, and the company's financial information is verified. This step includes a detailed examination of the financial statements, transaction records, and internal control systems.
- c. Reporting Phase: Organizing the audit findings and writing the audit report. The audit report includes the auditor's opinions, identified issues, and recommendations.

External Audit Risk

External audit risk refers to the possibility that an auditor may unintentionally fail to issue an appropriate opinion on financial statements containing material misstatements (Ruhnke et al., 2018). According to Muir (2018), it occurs when an external auditor provides a correct opinion on financial statements that are materially misstated, or issues an incorrect opinion when the statements are free from material misstatements. Similarly, Cindori (2018) defines audit risk as “the likelihood of expressing an incorrect opinion on the examined financial statements due to the auditor failing to detect existing material misstatements.” The International Federation of Accountants (IFAC) describes audit risk as the risk that results in an inappropriate auditor opinion when the financial statements are materially misstated (Niemi et al., 2018). Kesimli (2019) also highlights audit risk as the auditor issuing an incorrect opinion when significant misstatements are present. Overall, audit risk can be analyzed from two distinct perspectives.

First is the risk of improper rejection, when the auditor incorrectly rejects the financial statements that appear to be sound.

Second is the risk of misunderstanding, meaning the client accepts the financial statements by submitting a clean report, even though these financial statements contain material errors.

Results

First: Presentation and Analysis of the Results of the Variables in Light of the Research Sample

The table below shows the average responses of the research sample members who completed the questionnaire and the degree of consistency of their responses:

Table 1. Arithmetic Means and Standard Deviations for the Cloud Computing Technology Variable

No	Paragraphs	Mean	S.D
1	Cloud computing technology provides ample storage space for files.	4.17	0.76
2	Cloud computing technology protects files from viruses.	4.27	0.63
3	Cloud computing technology is easy to use for the external auditor.	3.79	1.09
4	Cloud computing technology provides the external auditor with easy access to available data.	3.63	0.91
5	Cloud computing technology enables the external auditor to continue working from anywhere, at any time.	4.60	0.72
6	Cloud computing technology provides its services to the external auditor at a low cost.	4.27	0.56
7	Cloud computing technology helps the external auditor access data without having to download it.	4.12	0.90
8	Cloud computing technology allows the external auditor to complete their work quickly.	3.96	0.84
9	Cloud computing technology contributes to the external auditor's impartial opinion.	4.46	0.67
10	Cloud computing technology contributes to the efficiency of the external auditor's work.	4.12	0.83

Source: Prepared by the researcher

From the table above, it is clear that the highest arithmetic mean was achieved in the fifth indicator, as it achieved an arithmetic mean of (4.60), which is higher than the hypothetical mean of (3), and a standard deviation of (0.72). This indicates that the sample's answers were consistent with the indicator, as providing cloud computing technology, if available, provides an incentive to work on a continuous basis. The fourth indicator achieved an arithmetic mean of (3.63), which is also higher than the hypothetical mean of (3), and a standard deviation of (0.91). Although the sample's answers were consistent with the indicator, it needs a reinforcement aspect, according to the sample's opinion.

Table 2. Means and Standard Deviations of the External Auditor's Performance Variable

No	Paragraphs	Mean	S.D
Dimension: External Auditor Neutrality			
11	The external auditor must be independent of the company being audited.	4.15	0.85
12	The external auditor must follow certain standards to ensure their impartiality.	3.65	0.76
13	The external auditor must issue periodic reports on their work to ensure their impartiality.	4.06	0.85
14	The external auditor must follow professional ethical standards to ensure their impartiality.	4.27	0.60
15	The external auditor must be subject to independent oversight to ensure their impartiality.	3.96	0.84
Dimension: External Auditor Competence			
16	The external auditor must be highly competent.	4.56	0.57

17	The external auditor must handle sensitive information confidentially.	4.52	0.61
18	The quality of the external auditor's report is directly proportional to their competence.	4.27	0.63
19	The external auditor has the ability to provide efficient and distinguished audit services that benefit the company.	4.35	0.79
20	The external auditor has the ability to make effective recommendations that improve the company's financial policies.	4.25	0.60

Source: Prepared by the researcher

Analysis of the table indicates that the fourteenth indicator within the dimension of external auditor neutrality recorded the highest arithmetic mean of 4.27, exceeding the hypothetical mean of 3, with a standard deviation of 0.60, placing it first among the indicators in this dimension. This suggests a strong agreement among the sample respondents regarding this indicator. In contrast, the twelfth indicator achieved an arithmetic mean of 3.65, also above the hypothetical mean of 3, but with a higher standard deviation of 0.76, ranking it last within the same dimension. Regarding the dimension of external auditor efficiency, the sixteenth indicator attained the highest arithmetic mean of 4.56, with a standard deviation of 0.57, making it the top-ranked indicator. Conversely, the twenty-second indicator recorded an arithmetic mean of 4.25 and a standard deviation of 0.60, placing it last among the indicators in this dimension.

Second: Testing the Influence Relationships between the Main Research Variables

This section is dedicated to examining the impact of the independent variable, cloud computing technology, on the dependent variable, external auditor performance, in accordance with the main hypothesis, which posits that “there is a statistically significant effect of cloud computing technology on the development of external auditor performance.” A simple linear regression model was employed for this analysis. The overall level of the model was used to assess the significance of the independent variable's influence on the dependent variable. The decision to accept or reject the influence hypothesis is made by comparing the calculated F-value with the critical F-value at two significance levels (0.05 and 0.01), as outlined below:

Table 3. Shows the Impact of Cloud Computing Technology and the Development of External Auditor Performance

Model*	Non-standard transactions	Standard transactions	T value	T indication	
	B	S . E	β		
Cloud computing technology	0.172	0.362	-	0.476	0.637
Developing the performance of the external auditor	0.951	0.101	0.822	9.421	0.000
ANOVA indication	0.000				
Correlation coefficient R	0.822				
Coefficient of determination R ²	0.760				

Source: Prepared by the researcher

The analysis of the table indicates a positive correlation between the independent variable, "cloud computing technology," and the dependent variable, "improvement in external auditor performance." Specifically, the t-value for the independent variable is 9.421, exceeding the critical table value, with a significance level of 0.000, which is below the statistical threshold of 0.005. Conversely, the regression intercept was found to be statistically insignificant, as its significance

level of 0.637 exceeds 0.05, suggesting that the intercept should be excluded from the model. The applied model employs a linear regression framework confirmed by a significant ANOVA result ($p = 0.000$). The correlation coefficient of 0.82 demonstrates a strong positive relationship between the two variables, while the coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.760, indicating that cloud computing technology accounts for 76% of the variance in the dependent variable. This represents a substantial contribution to explaining the changes in auditor performance.

The Impact of Implementing Cloud Computing Technology on Strengthening the Neutrality of the External Auditor

The calculated value of (f) reached (37.018), which is greater than its tabular value of (2.27) at a significance level of (0.01), and (1.90) at a significance level of (0.05) and a degree of freedom of (1.118). This means that implementing cloud computing technology has a clear impact on strengthening the neutrality of the external auditor, leading to the ease and speed of completing work with impartiality by the external auditor, clearly, and thus the correct work of the external auditor. The value of the coefficient of determination reached (0.24%), which means that implementing cloud computing technology explains (0.24%) of the fluctuations that occur in strengthening the neutrality of the external auditor, which confirms the validity of the first sub-hypothesis. The value of (b) reached (0.489), meaning that a change in the implementation of cloud computing technology by one unit indicates strengthening the neutrality of the external auditor. By (0.489) as shown in Table (4):

Table 4. Results of the Impact of Applying Cloud Computing Technology in Strengthening the Neutrality of the External Auditor

Source of variance	sum of squares	degree of freedom	mean squares	Total F value	β	R^2
Regression	12,320	1	12,320	018,37	0,489	0.24
Error	39,272	118	0,333			
Total	51,592	119				

Source: Prepared by the researcher

The Impact of Implementing Cloud Computing Technology on Increasing the Efficiency of the External Auditor

The calculated value of (f) reached (28.187), which is greater than its tabular value of (2.27) at a significance level of (0.01), and (1.90) at a significance level of (0.05) and a degree of freedom of (1.118), which confirms that the implementation of cloud computing technology has an impact on increasing the efficiency of the external auditor. The value of the coefficient of determination reached (0.20%), which means that the implementation of cloud computing technology explains (0.20%) of the fluctuations that occur in increasing the efficiency of the external auditor. This confirms the validity of the second sub-hypothesis. The value of (b) reached (0.439), meaning that a change in the implementation of cloud computing technology by one unit indicates a change in increasing the efficiency of the external auditor by (0.439), as shown in Table No. (5):

Table 5. Results of the Impact of Applying Cloud Computing Technology on Increasing the Efficiency of the External Auditor

Source of variance	sum of squares	degree of freedom	mean squares	Total F value	β	R^2
Regression	8,867	1	9,948	28,187	0,439	0.20
Error	42,724	118	0,353			
Total	51,592	119				

Source: Prepared by the researcher

Conclusions

1. There exists a positive relationship between the independent variable, cloud computing technology, and the dependent variable, the enhancement of external auditor performance.
2. The implementation of cloud computing technology has a clear impact on strengthening the impartiality of the external auditor.
3. The implementation of cloud computing technology leads to the ease and speed of conducting work with impartiality by the external auditor.
4. The implementation of cloud computing technology has an impact on increasing the efficiency of the external auditor.
5. The results showed that the use of cloud computing technology contributes to reducing the time required to access financial data, thus increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of auditing.
6. Cloud computing technology provides flexible and real-time access to accounting records by external auditors.

Recommendations

1. The need to qualify and train auditors to deal with and use cloud computing technology.
2. Efforts should be made to issue clear professional standards regarding the use of cloud computing.
3. It is necessary to strive to update the curricula of academic departments specializing in accounting to include the use of cloud computing technology.

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